

LABOR DISPUTES AND STRIKES

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Abstract. This article deals with the consideration of labor disputes and strikes in society in accordance with the labor legislation and the procedures for finding a solution to them.

Keywords: employee, conflict, attitude, criteria, team, law, contract, competent authority, participant, social, reason, principle.

ТРУДОВЫЕ СПОРЫ И ЗАБАСТОВКИ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена рассмотрению трудовых споров и забастовок в обществе в соответствии с трудовым законодательством и процедурам поиска их решения.

Ключевые слова: сотрудник, конфликт, отношение, критерии, команда, закон, контракт, компетентный орган, участник, социальный, разум, принцип.

Enter. First of all, while talking about labor disputes and strikes, we will dwell on their origin, essence and consequences. Disputes in the field of labor are conflicts of organizational labor relations, characterized by direct social conflicts between individuals and groups of employees. The statute does not create any organizational labor disputes. Such a situation arises in the following cases, if:

- if the conflicts reflect mutually exclusive points of view of the subjects;
- if the level of conflicts is high enough;
- if the conflicts are easy to understand, i.e. if individuals and groups understand these conflicts or, on the contrary, if they are incomprehensible;
- when conflicts arise immediately, unexpectedly, or accumulate for a long time before some social conflicts arise.

There are open and closed conflicts depending on the nature and degree of manifestation of the signs of conflicts in the field of labor. The main criteria for dividing into these types are as follows:

- level of understanding of the conflict situation, its subjects, reasons and perspectives;
- the presence or absence of real conflicting transactions, activity in the sphere of its regulation;
- the fact that the conflict situation is known to the surrounding people and their influence on this situation;

Closed (private) conflicts are often uncomfortable. They often have a destructive effect on the organization and organizational labor relations, and there are very few opportunities to solve them. In closed disputes, not only individuals, but also groups become a source of mutual quarrels, they do not have the opportunity to influence negative processes. In addition to the individual, there are also conflicts related to collective work. Consideration of collective labor disputes is regulated by Chapter 61 of the Labor Code of the Russian Federation. Collective labor disputes - this is the refusal to take into account the opinion of the representative body elected by the employer in the adoption of documents of the working conditions between workers and the employer or his representatives, including drawing up, changing and changing wages, collective agreements and agreements. unresolved disputes regarding access; including labor legislation. Employers must take into account the requirements of the employees sent to them. The procedure for solving a collective labor dispute consists of the following stages:

1. Consideration of the collective labor dispute by the conciliation commission;
2. Consideration of a collective labor dispute with the participation of a mediator;
3. Consideration of a collective labor dispute in labor arbitration.

The conciliation commission is established within 3 working days from the moment of the collective labor dispute. The decision to establish a commission is formalized by the appropriate order of the employer and the decision of the employee's representative. The conciliation commission is made up of representatives of the parties on an equal basis. The parties to the collective labor dispute may not withdraw from the formation of the conciliation commission. The dispute must be considered within five working days from the date of creation of the commission. This period can be extended by mutual agreement of the parties. The decision of the conciliation commission is adopted according to the agreement of the parties and is formalized in a protocol that is binding for both parties and must be executed within the time limit set by the commission. If no mutual agreement is reached in the conciliation commission, the parties will continue the procedures with the participation of a mediator. The parties to the labor dispute may invite a mediator within three working days after the conciliation commission draws up a report on the disagreements. If the parties do not reach an agreement on the candidate of the mediator within three days, they should proceed to create a labor arbitration. Labor arbitration is a temporary body for consideration of a collective labor dispute if the parties have agreed in writing on the binding of their decisions. Arbitration shall be established by the parties to the dispute in conjunction with the collective labor dispute resolution service no later than three business days after consideration by the dispute commission or mediator. The creation of labor arbitration, its composition, rules of procedure, powers are formalized by the appropriate decision of the employer and the employee's representative. The created arbitration hearing considers the appeal of the parties to the collective labor dispute for up to 5 days and develops recommendations for its resolution. If the employer refuses to establish a labor arbitration, as well as refuses to comply with its recommendations, the workers can go on strike.

Analysis of literature on the topic (Literature review). There are different definitions of the concept of labor dispute in the legal literature. According to some scientists, labor disputes in the broadest sense are labor legislation, labor and collective agreements, which occur in connection with the application of collective agreements or in connection with the creation of an employment contract, regulated by normative legal documents. not included are disputes between the subjects of labor relations related to the creation of new working conditions, which are usually considered as a trade union (or with their participation) or another method determined by legislative bodies. Another group of scientists understand individual labor dispute as a dispute between an employee and an employer regarding the application of labor regulations adopted by law, collective agreements, agreements, terms of the labor contract (contract) by the competent authorities. Still other scientists define labor disputes as "disagreements between an employee and an employer regarding the definition and application of applicable norms of labor and other social legislation, which are directly negotiated by the employees concerned (or their representatives) with the employer. It is understood as "a case that has not been resolved in negotiations and has turned into a dispute, which has been dealt with in the labor dispute commission (MNK) or in court". According to American researchers, 85% of a person's success in the labor market depends on his quickness and foresight in solving emerging problems, and 15% depends on his professional skills. The interests of the employer and the employee he hires do not always coincide, so a conflict of these interests can occur at any stage of the development and development of labor relations, which causes conflicts. Working conditions that do not meet the established standards, inefficient management that ignores the legal interests of employees - the subjects of labor relations - all this, as a rule, can cause disputes between the parties in labor legal relations.

Analysis and results. The agreement of the parties to the collective labor dispute is made in writing and is binding for the parties. If the conciliation proceedings do not lead to the resolution of the collective labor dispute, the employees or their representatives may start organizing a strike. According to the rules of Art. Article 37 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation recognizes the right of workers to strike as a way to resolve a collective labor dispute. Workers' participation in the strike is voluntary. No one shall be forced to participate in a strike or strike. The employer's representatives have no right to organize a strike

and participate in it. The current Labor Code of the Russian Federation defines the right to strike, the procedure for announcing it, the governing body, the obligations of the parties, the prohibition of illegal strikes, as well as the guarantees and legal status of workers related to workers and their responsibility for participating in illegal strikes. According to their content, labor disputes are divided into collective and individual labor disputes. Personal disputes are disputes between a specific employee and the administration, which usually arise in connection with the application of regulatory documents regulating the labor relations of employees. Disputes related to the team are disputes that concern all employees, arise in connection with the introduction of new working conditions or changes in existing working conditions, as well as the administration's fulfillment of its obligations to the entire team. According to their nature, labor disputes are divided into lawsuit disputes and non-lawsuit disputes. Disputes in the nature of a lawsuit arise in connection with the application of normative acts on labor. During such a dispute, the employee tries to restore his rights by filing a lawsuit. They always have a personal character. Disputes that do not have the character of a lawsuit include disputes arising in connection with the change of existing working conditions or the introduction of new working conditions. They can have a personal character, as well as a collective character. Individuals and groups directly and indirectly related to the conflict are its subjects. They can be divided into the following categories: primary agents, participating participants, environment.

As the primary agents of conflicts in the field of labor, some employees, labor groups, some groups of organizations come to the fore, and their interests collide in the labor process and distribution relations. Conflicts occur either voluntarily and consciously, with secondary participants joining, or primary agents attract more and more participants. This merger happens for many reasons. When the social base of conflicts expands, the problem that creates the conflict itself can become more complicated and confusing. This will create better conditions for conflict resolution. The conflict environment is caused by the fact that some individuals or groups are neutrally looking at the situation or refraining from interfering in order to relax it, or they are interested in the continuation of the conflict situation and behave in a wait-and-see way. Labor disputes themselves will end in a positive way. Causes of labor disputes Researching the causes of labor disputes allows to determine the possibilities and principles of their resolution.

Conclusion and recommendations. The most effective means of resolving conflicts in the field of labor legislation is social partnership. It is the participants of social partnerships based on the principle of tripartism that create the regime of legality in labor relations. But the development of social partnership in our country is at a slow level, therefore, many disputes that can be resolved by the parties' agreement processes are submitted for consideration by state authorities - courts. A strike is a last resort to resolve a collective labor dispute. Strike - in cases that may endanger people's lives and health, as well as in railway and urban public transport, including the subway, civil aviation, communication, energy, defense industry enterprises, state bodies, the defense capability of the Republic Strikes are not allowed in enterprises and organizations entrusted with the task of ensuring law and order and security, and in continuously operating production enterprises, the suspension of which may lead to serious and dangerous consequences. The general and continuous length of service of the employee participating in the strike, the right to receive insurance under the state social insurance will be preserved, and the employees participating in the non-prohibited strikes will also have their job. The wages of the employees participating in the strike will not be withheld. Employees who did not participate in the strike, but were unable to perform their work due to the strike, must be paid wages paid by the enterprise, institution, organization for the time the employee was absent without fault. In conclusion, we should mention that, if labor disputes and the material and financial needs of workers are not up to the required level, strikes will erupt in that society, and this will not only increase the demand for labor force, but also cause the gradual decline of the country. . It is no exaggeration to say that if the above-mentioned needs of the employee are fully covered and additional incentives are given to the employee in order to prevent strikes and labor disputes, the desire of the employee to work will increase.

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